

THE INTERCONNECTED REALMS OF MAYA COSMOLOGICAL PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract: After establishing the fundamental physics prizes, Yuri Milner said: “Unlike the Nobel in physics, the Fundamental Physics Prize can be awarded to scientists whose ideas have not yet been verified by experiments, which often occurs decades later. Sometimes a radical new idea “really deserves recognition right away because it expands our understanding of at least what is possible”. Keeping this mind, the author disseminates Mayan’s model of cosmology.

Keywords: Pre-big bang; Particles; Space; Matter; Energy; Expansion; Contraction

Introduction

"The Science related to numerical order enables one to know the principles of role of number, space order nature of inner space and significantly know the potency of micro-structure. (Atoms)" Mayan's Ainthiram ...page 347

Ainthiram refers to a text written during the first Sangam period in ancient Tamil land -South of India (10,000 BC). The name refers to the fivefold process of consciousness transforming itself into the material world - or energy transforming into matter. This is a scientific process according to Mayan the Rishi who cognized this process and wrote the Ainthiram. It reflects the fundamental enfoldments of the quantum field into waveforms that make up the material world. Mayan stated that this process could be replicated by humans in dance, music, poetry, sculpture and architecture (Vaastu architecture).

This formed the basis of traditional arts in India for thousands of years.

In the Ainthiram, Mayan speaks of the unfolding of letters (visual forms) from what he called OM Light; and, sounds of consonants and vowels (aural forms) from what he called OM Sound. He indicates this phenomenon by beginning every verse of his commentary on the Ainthiram (called the Pranava Veda - first Veda) with Oli, Oli indicating OM Light and OM Sound. OM, being a universal sound and light form and not a Sanskrit term nor a Hindu term. These are the only texts in ancient literature that mention both OM Light and OM Sound. In addition, they are the only texts that elucidate the manifestation process as both a spiritual and scientific process.

In Tamil' Aintu' stands for five. The five aspects are

1. The primary source of creation (Moola)

2. The vibration factor leading to creation or the Time factor (Kalam)

3. The order inherent in the vibration (seelam)

4. Form emerging from the primary source through the vibration (kolam) and

5. Finally the end result being the form emerging from the primary source through the vibration (kolam) and finally the end result being the all-encompassing universe.

The following is a summary of some of the principles put forth by Mayan in the Ainthiram, the Tamil text of Indian Architectural philosophy.

1. All objects of nature are unified entities (forms) of energy and matter.

2. The free space is the unified field of energy and matter and source of all forms that we see in material world.

3. There are two OMs: OM Light and OM Sound, the former is the source of all visible objects and the later, the source of all aural forms.

4. All material forms of the universe are musical forms or have taken shape on musical rhythm or musical scale.

5. Time creates, sustains, and destroys all, so created.

6. The primal manifest form of the unmanifested is square (primal wave pattern).

7. The primal square pattern in designated as the diagram of embodied Energy - Vaastu Purusha mandala.

8. The free space is packed with cubical atoms of energy.

They are building blocks of the structure of the universe.

9. The cube is micro-adobe called Sittravai / Citrambalam) (mini hall in Tamil).

10. Within the hall there is a vertical luminous shaft called Brahma Sutra (Oli nool -)

11. The Oli nool / Brahma Sutra is a shaft of consciousness also called Moolathoon / Moolasthambham.

12. This shaft of consciousness vibrates in a particular order called rhythm. This is the order of nature.

13. This rhythmic vibration of the shaft of consciousness is the dance of Shiva, the Space.

14. The micro space, in the cubical shape is foetus, Garbha or Bindu. This is known as Vinkaru in Tamil.

15. This micro adobe is the repository of light and sound.

16. The free space is Light and the Light is Moola or source of the universe and universal forms. Light is Brahman, Atman, Vastu Brahman - Nunporul (in Tamil).

17. The embodied energy is Vaastu Brahman / Vastu Purusha. The space enclosed in a building is Prasada Purusha - energized building - building is a living organism, built of musical units of measure.

18. Architecture is the supreme achievement of mathematics. 19. Mathematics is rooted in the dynamism of Absolute Time.

20. Time is the vibration of Space.

21. Time and Space are equal.

22. Time is one of the subtle elements of Space (akasa).

23. Time is the causal element of all objects of the Universe.

24. The microcosmic structure is in total identity with macrocosmic structure.

25. The supreme space is throbbing every moment to express itself out.

26. Through the power of inner consciousness, the knower of Vastu should know about light aspects and sound aspects of OM pertaining to both inner and outer space.

27. Those who do not realize the creative dynamism of inner space cannot know the dynamism of outer space...

The language of physics is applied mathematics. The foundations of Einstein's general relativity is Non – Euclidean geometry and Tensors. Hamiltonian, Lagrangian and group theory are the basics for particle physics. In order to prove the above hypotheses, I politely propose the following theorems;

“If, in some cataclysm, all of scientific knowledge were to be destroyed, and only one sentence passed on to the next generations of creatures, what statement would contain the most information in the fewest words? I believe it is the atomic hypothesis (or the atomic fact, or whatever you wish to call it) that all things are made of atoms--little particles that move

References

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(1). There exists a spherical triangle whose interior angle sum is equal to 360 degrees.

(2). It is possible to draw a spherical triangle whose interior angle sum adds up to 540 degrees.

Discussion

The above hypotheses are to be proved. Readers may find it interesting that some of the above mentioned hypotheses agree with modern physics. The language of physics is applied mathematics. Non – Euclidean geometry and tensors are the basics for Einstein's general relativity, Hamiltonian, Lagrangian and group theories are the foundations for particle physics. In order to prove the above model of cosmology theoretically, I politely propose the following theorems:

(1) There exists a spherical triangle whose interior angle sum is equal to 360 degrees.

(2) It is possible to construct a spherical whose interior angle adds up to 540 degrees.

around in perpetual motion, attracting each other when they are a little distance apart, but repelling upon being squeezed into one another. In that one sentence, you will see, there is an enormous amount of information about the world, if just a little imagination and thinking are applied...”

Richard Feynman

Fabric of the Universe: The Origin, Application, and
Implication of Vastu Science and Vaastu
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